

Embracing Digital Technology in Kindergarten Instructions: Exploring the Post-pandemic Experiences of Teachers

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Abstract. This study explored the lived experiences of teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in post pandemic time particularly in Magpet, West District, Division of Cotabato, Region XI. There were ten (10) teachers who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the group of public kindergarten teachers in different schools of the same District. The virtual in-depth-interview was employed to gather some information with regards to their respective lived experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as pertains to the lived experiences of the participants: educators experiencing technological transitions, adaptability to change, becoming critical teachers, and hurdling technological constraints. There were three sub-themes that emerged from the challenges encountered by the participants. These are the lack of digital resources, intermittent connections, lack of cybersecurity and lack of expertise. The three coping mechanisms of teachers as participants in the challenges they experienced were: continuous professional development, personal learning, and collaborating with others. The two educational management insights drawn from the participants were the importance technological literacy in schools and the need to provide professional development trainings. With this, School leaders and administrators may establish school-based training sessions through Learning Action Cells (LAC). These sessions may assist teachers in developing the necessary skills to overcome knowledge gaps that hinder their ability to adapt to digital technology. Additionally, they may guarantee the availability of sufficient technical, administrative, and collegial support for teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital Technology 2. Lived Experiences 3. Kindergarten Teachers

Date Received: September 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: September 10, 2024 — Date Published: October 10, 2024

1. Introduction

The advent of technological advancements has facilitated the widespread integration of digital transformation across various sectors of productivity, including education and its associated components. This change can be attributed to the rapid growth of technologies, the digitization of various processes and resources, and the escalating user demand for adopting the latest technological advancements. The COVID-19 pandemic expedited the assimilation of digital technologies as both small and large organizations across many industries sought strategies to sustain operations. One advantage of this sense of urgency is that it demonstrated the potential

benefits of incorporating modifications in daily operations into contingency planning and enhancing resilience in the field of education. The global impact of information and communication technology, together with the internet, has significantly transformed the parameters of educational institutions worldwide. In light of this, educators, who serve as the principal agents responsible for driving and implementing digitalization inside educational settings, face the imperative of remaining current and enhancing their knowledge and skills in alignment with the most recent advancements and developments. In addition to enhancing classroom technology and software through the allocation of their own financial and material resources, educators must also possess fundamental and occasionally advanced knowledge in order to effectively fulfill their roles as authentic 21st-century instructors. Prior to the onset of the pandemic, some businesses exhibited resistance towards the concept of digitalization. However, as evidenced by Microsoft's data in 2022, the utilization of remote collaboration tools facilitated the connectivity of over 75 million individuals, effectively overcoming the constraints imposed by physical separation. Technology has played a crucial role in facilitating various activities, such as contact tracing for public health organizations, food delivery services for restaurants and grocery stores, e-commerce platforms for retailers, information dissemination for government agencies and news outlets, online learning platforms for educational institutions, and supply chain analytics for distributors and couriers. Historically in 2006, the Texas legislature enacted a law mandating the incorporation of technology application standards into K-12 curriculum. Davidson et al. (2014) devised these guidelines to aid educators in integrating technology into their classrooms in a way that enhances student learning. CAEP revised and updated 2008 criteria. Beginning in 2013, these technology guidelines were to be implemented in classrooms (CAEP, 2016). Teachers are expected to demonstrate a functional knowledge of digital technology in their classrooms and impart this information to their students. In addition, a significant number of students enrolled in Texas elementary schools reside at or below the poverty line and rely on government assistance to acquire basic necessities. Typically, these institutions have a greater student-to-teacher ratio. Teachers at this institution have observed that students lack the prerequisite knowledge that many of their peers of the same age possess when entering the classroom, and that teachers lack the specific knowledge and materials necessary to teach lessons with the aid of technology (Tirrell-Corbin Cooper, 2014). In order to prepare students for the future, it was unquestionable that the majority of educators endeavor to incorporate technology into the classroom. During the pandemic, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology in Indonesia adopted a policy for distance learning (Kemendikbud, 2020). It governs how remote learning is conducted in the absence of direct teacher-student interaction. Consequently, educational materials are distributed via the media. Distance education is inextricably linked to e-Learning, which utilizes the connectivity, accessibility, and adaptability of internet networks to facilitate a range of learning experiences. One could argue that DL significantly relies on technology to provide anytime, anywhere access to knowledge and learning resources. However, the dearth of digital literacy skills among teachers hinders the implementation of DL (Putria et al., 2020). As with the rest of the world, the COVID-19 pandemic has altered digital life in the Philippines. As the nation contends with lockdowns and school closures, the people become more reliant on the Internet and technological devices to maintain contact with the larger society. The government acknowledged, in light of contemporary issues, that digital literacy is necessary for pupils to keep up with the rate at which tech-

nologies become smarter. According to Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization or SEAMEO (2021), the Department of Education implemented programs to promote information, media, and technology competencies. According to their study, even though students are becoming digital natives, there is still much work to be done to transform them into responsible digital citizens. This cannot be achieved if instructors do not increase their knowledge and expertise in digital citizenship and digital literacy. Educators must have the pedagogical skills necessary to aid students in developing their digital citizenship skills. In the local context, notably in Magpet West District, kindergarten school teachers understand that the primary goal of elementary education is to aid the intellectual, social, physical, and psychological development of all children. Nonetheless, achieving these goals remains a challenge in the Philippine educational system, notably for Key Stage 1 and 2 students (Kindergarten through Grade 6). Considering the difficulties associated with implementing the Basic Education Learning Con-

tinuity Plan (BE-LCP) and even the face-to-face post pandemic curriculum, where proficiency in the digital world has become a requirement, the pandemic taught everyone that schools are not just places for academic learning and that technology plays a crucial role in ensuring that learning continuity occurs in the lives of learners, including those enrolled in the distance modular modality before. Despite increased access to and use of digital technology, digital disparities continue to exist not only among students but also among teachers, preventing the most vulnerable children from acquiring the digital skills necessary for lifelong learning. As a researcher, I would like to characterize the digital literacy or technological competence of teachers in order to comprehend the dilemma they face when it comes to implementing technology in the classroom during the post-pandemic era. I believe that teachers and students will become overwhelmed as technology evolves if they are not exposed to learning platforms that initiate digital literacy programs and are not equipped with the necessary knowledge.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the experiences of the teachers in becoming digital immigrants or technology experts in public elementary schools. The challenges of the kindergarten teachers in the post pandemic time, as well as their insights, shall be determined at the end of this study, particularly in Magpet, West District, Division of Cotabato.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of kindergarten teachers on the challenges they experience at present as they utilize technology in their kindergarten instructions?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of kindergarten teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Digital technologies. Encompass a range of technological tools and resources employed to facilitate the process of teaching and learning. These include but are

not limited to computers, tablets, mobile phones, online resources, digital tools, electronic devices, and various other resources. Digital tools have the capability to generate, store, and manipulate data. Digital literacy. This refers to the technical knowledge and utilization skills of

ICT tools used in the teaching-learning process. This also refers to the ability to use formal operational skills, along with analytical, content creation, and media literacy skills, to navigate the Internet and retrieve information. This is a necessary competency or a skill to attain success in the digital environment and involves the confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for education, work, and participation in society. (Council of the European Union, 2018) Digital immigrants.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Personnel. The DepEd, particularly the Magpet, West District, Division of Cotabato. to look into their capacity enhancement programs and trainings to help teachers to become technologically inclined particularly in their teaching and learning processes and activities. This study shall provide information on the real situation of the elementary teachers with regards to their competence and knowledge on technology in the post-pandemic time. School Principals and Headteachers. For the school principals and school, heads to gain a clear understanding of teachers' competence to become digital native teachers. This may also be their basis for future capacity enhancement

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is grounded in Kolb's experiential learning theory. Educators who acquire proficiency in utilizing technology, be it through classroom pedagogy or other methodologies, actively engage in the process of learning (Kolb, 1981). The concept of expanding one's knowledge, as demonstrated by Kolb's experiential learning theory (Kolb, 1981), serves as an illustrative example. Subsequently, these instructors were capable of

These are the teachers who were not born into the digital world but have, later in their lives, adapted to and began to use new technologies. (Gallardo, et al., 2015). Post-pandemic times. This is the current phase in the society which is considered as a period of transition wherein the world and national economy are anticipated to recover and resume full-scale business operations subsequent to the significant disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic on workplaces, education and businesses.

programs for teachers who lack technological competence, understanding, and skills. Kindergarten and other school teachers. The findings of the study shall provide the scenario as to how teachers are challenged to utilize digital technologies in schools. The study may share its lessons learned to other teachers who are experiencing the same issues and problems, if there are any. Future researchers. This study also provides research literature which could also serve as basis for future researchers who would wish to conduct a study parallel to the themes of this study and or applying other categories that their study will cover. The study could be a strong basis especially for those who will engage in qualitative research employing phenomenology or in other words, this would serve as reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

leveraging their technology proficiency to facilitate opportunities for their students to engage in scholarly pursuits. Educators successfully imparted knowledge to their students by incorporating accessible technology into their lesson plans and student activities, hence enhancing the students' understanding of the subjects being taught. This enabled the students to utilize technology more efficiently in order to achieve a better understanding of concepts. As students

engaged in the learning process, they advanced within Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) while acquiring knowledge on various subjects (Vygotsky, 1978). Additionally, this study is further substantiated by George Siemens's connectivism thesis, which posits that digital literacy is a pertinent learning theory in the context of the digital world. According to the connectivist theory, the process of learning takes place through the establishment and development of links. It is imperative for educators to facilitate the process of linking prior knowledge with new information for students. Additionally, students should possess the ability to recognize deficiencies in their own knowledge. The advent of technology has significantly expanded the capacity of students to autonomously access the most current knowledge pertaining to any given subject. The promotion of this particular mode of self-directed learning and exploration is highly encouraged. Connectivism is founded on the fundamental proposition that the process of learning is no longer exclusively confined to internal cognitive processes. It is imperative that students are afforded the chance to engage in the integration of knowledge and ideas, to independently pursue comprehension, and to engage in collaborative endeavors facilitated by technological means. The objective of this study was to facilitate the acquisition of detailed accounts of personal experiences from the educators participating in the interviews, while concurrently enabling the researcher to gather vivid and precise descriptions of said experiences. This inquiry establishes a linkage to the experiential learning theory established by David Kolb (1981). In order to get insight into the utilization of technology in the classroom by adult educators, it was imperative to ascertain their acquisition of technological knowledge and skills. According to Kolb's (1981) theoretical framework, adult learners engage in the process of utilizing their prior experiences as a means to acquire and assimilate new concepts. Numerous educators are acquiring technological proficiency concurrently with their students. Certain individuals receive professional growth in technological applications, while others do not. According to Varier et al. (2017), individuals across different levels of expertise are encountering technology and its applications in educational settings, and are leveraging their understanding to instruct their students.

2. Methodology

Presented in this chapter is the method. It includes the Philosophical Assumption, Qualitative Assumption, Design and Procedure, Research, Participants, Role of the Researcher, Data Collection, Data Analysis, and Trustworthiness of the Study.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumptions in my study were used in analyzing and interpreting my results. At its most basic level, psychological research can be used to explain and forecast parts of the human experience, improve our understanding of the lived experiences of different groups of people, or criticize and change the current conditions in which we live and seek to grow (Lincoln, Lynham, Guba, 2013). According to Creswell (2012), the ontological issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. Qualitative researchers embrace the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities by exploring multiple forms of evidence from different individuals' perspectives and experiences. Hence, when studying individuals, I as a qualitative researcher conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. With the epistemological assumption, as a researcher, I aim to become as close to the people I am studying as possible. The individual perspectives I gathered from the field research are used to compile subjective evidence. Therefore, conducting a qualitative study means that I tried to get as close as possible to the participants being studied collecting subjective evidences assembled based on individual views. Since epistemology is concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge are possible and how we can ensure that they are both adequate and legitimate, I was able to discover how knowledge is known, through the subjective experiences of people. These are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the field or get to know the participants, the

more they know what they know from firsthand information (Guba Lincoln, 2008). Qualitative researchers make their values clear in a study, whereas quantitative researchers bring their values to a study. This is the axiological assumption that qualitative research is based on. In this study, I acknowledged the study's value-laden nature and actively reported their values and prejudices, as well as the value-laden nature of field data (Creswell, 2012). Qualitative research processes, or rhetorics, are described as inductive, emergent, and influenced by my experience gathering and evaluating data. Rather than being handed down wholly from a theory or from the perspectives of the inquirer, the logic I shall follow is inductive, starting from the ground up. During the data analysis, I'll take a step-by-step approach to examining the data in order to gain a more in-depth understanding of the subject at hand.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Individuals want to comprehend their reality and generate their own unique meanings that correlate to their experiences using Social Constructivism

as an interpretative framework for qualitative assumptions (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are not imprinted or innate in each person. Rather, meanings emerge as a result of inter-

actions with others (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are varied and multiple, leading the researcher to look for the complexity of views rather than narrow the meanings into a few categories or ideas. Further, as a researcher, my purpose is to rely as much as possible on the perspectives of the participants. These subjective

meanings are frequently disputed in social and historical contexts. In other words, they are developed through interactions with others as well as historical and cultural conventions that work in people's lives, rather than being merely imprinted on them.

2.3. Design and Procedure—The study was conducted using a qualitative-inquiry-based phenomenological research design using open-ended questions. Phenomenological research is a kind of investigation in which the researcher identifies the essence of participants' descriptions of a phenomenon. The researcher brackets or sets aside his or her own experiences in order to understand the experiences of the study participants (Creswell Creswell, 2017). The researcher was able to produce a description of the teachers' shared meanings with regard to their digital literacy efforts through technology-based teaching and learning practices while emphasizing the similarity of their experiences (Creswell, 2007). Phenomenological approaches are particularly effective at bringing to the fore individual experiences and perceptions from their own points of view, and so challenging structural or normative assumptions. Adding an interpretive component to phenomenological research allows it to inform, support, or question policy and action by allowing it to be utilized as the foundation for practical theory (Lester et al., 2009). As a result, the research methodology is a good fit for capturing the thoughts and experiences of teachers seeking professional development amidst the Covid-19 outbreak. According to Bogart (2017), gaining a clearer image of the occurrence will aid in filling research gaps and

providing suggestions for improvement, which in the context of the current study refers to teacher professional development through webinars. The study attempted to present the "living worlds" of the participants, finally exposing their personal relevance in relation to the experience, as a design that captures the experiences of a "chosen few" addressing specific phenomena. Further, this study also employed participants' observations in an In-Depth Interview (IDI). According to Denzel Lincoln (2000), as cited by Lee (2007) in Pelobello (2015), this method involves the use and collection of variety of interviews, observations, history, interactional and visual texts that describe routines, problems and meaning of individual lives. It is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions that explore a social or human problem. It builds a holistic picture, analyzes words, reports, detailed views of informants, and conducts the study in a natural setting. Furthermore, real life situations need to be explored in terms of their contextual nature as seen by the participants. Therefore, phenomenology is an appropriate and applicable technique to explore the topics on the lived experiences of kindergarten educators in public elementary schools. Common themes will be analyzed, coded and extracted from all of the interviews.

2.4. Research Participants—This study was conducted in DepEd Region XII, Division of Cotabato specifically in Magpet, West

District. Only 10 participants from 10 different public elementary schools as the key informants were included and were purposely se-

lected based on the nature of their work as classroom teachers and who already experienced working in the Department of Education for at least three years or more. The purposive sampling technique, also called judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of an informant due to the qualities the informant possesses. According to Bernard (2006), it is a non-random technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants. It was the researcher who decided what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience. Purposive sampling is exemplified through the key informant technique wherein one or a few individuals are solicited to act as guides to the phenomenon. Key informants are

observant, reflective members of the community of interest who know much about the topic and are both able and willing to share their knowledge. To gain a variance in perspective from participants, effort was extended to include both male and female as well as individuals with various levels of educational training, attainment and rank. Specifically, the inclusion criteria include the following: (1) Teachers who have been teaching for three or more years in DepEd; (2) had experienced attending Teachers' Professional Development sessions on becoming technologically inclined classroom instructors before and during the pandemic; and (3) teachers who have been teaching in the kindergarten level.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation The participants were adequately informed about the research undertaking through an informed consent. Consent was given freely and the researcher made sure that the participants understood what was being asked and emphasized that their participations were just purely voluntary. All participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached individually online and given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were also given an appropriate time to ask questions and address concerns. It was explained that their participation was voluntary; they may also refuse to participate or withdraw from the study while it was in progress. When the participants agreed to be part of the In-Depth Interview (IDI), a date, time, and venue were set.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis and reporting of the study findings. Pri-

vacy and confidentiality of the interview environment were managed carefully during the interview sessions, data analysis and dissemination of the findings. The confidentiality of handling the data is in accordance to Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Interview Sessions Each interview was conducted individual through online. The interview was done with the use of google meet, google sheets and messenger application. The researcher was the only knowledgeable person who can match the identity of the participants in voice and in video recordings. In recording the data, interviews were audio-taped and video recorded with the permission of the participants, and the voice records were transcribed verbatimly. Some notes were taken by the researcher to have genuine, accurate and authentic transcription but the identification of the information of the participants were removed or disguised. Further, the interviews, transcriptions and consent forms were kept in a secured location. To safeguard confidentiality, consent forms were stored in a separate location from the other data so there is no way they can be linked to the interviews.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—In qualitative research, the researcher’s role is to try to gain access to the needed data while exploring the research participants’ ideas and feelings on the phenomenon being studied. This is not a simple task, to say the least. This entails inviting people to discuss topics that are potentially highly personal to them. Reliving prior experiences

might be tough at times when the experiences being explored are somehow negative to them and are still fresh in the participant’s thoughts. My first job as a researcher is to protect participants and their data in any method that data is acquired. Participants shall be given explicit and articulated mechanisms for such safeguarding.

2.7. *Data Collection*—In gathering the data, I prepared the interview guide which is composed of three (3) main significant questions which inquired about the experiences of teachers. A thorough deliberation was made on the aspect of determining the problems of teachers in their effort to become digital immigrants in schools. I made sure that my interview guide was validated by the experts. Moreover, I made sure that all ethical protocols were observed and implemented as I collected the data. An official letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, DepEd Division Office, San Roque District Office and the principals of San Roque district Schools asking permission to conduct the study. After receiving the approval letter, the conditions set by the approving authority will be considered and met. Then, the interview sessions followed. The interviews were conducted in public places with private areas to protect confidentiality for some of the participants and since the study was conducted during the pandemic - COVID-19, Facebook Messenger, Google Sheets, Zoom and Google meet were also used to other participants to adhere to the protocols issued by the Department of Health and the Inter-Agency task Force. The interviews were audio recorded with the consent of the participants. In addition, participants were asked to refrain from using names during the interview (names of people and places).

At each interview, I discussed the purpose of the study, the structure of the interview and the nature, benefits and risks of participation were discussed with the participants. They were, likewise, informed that participation is voluntary and that all the information gathered are held with strict measures of confidentiality. They were informed that there is no financial compensation for their participation and their participation could raise awareness and provide insight on the phenomenon being investigated. Right after, the transcription of In-depth Interviews (IDI) proceedings was done with the help of the note taker and recorder. I also utilized Inscribe software trial version in transcribing the participants’ responses and I also ensured the authentic responses of the informants. In the process, I was able to establish rapport with the interviewees to elicit honest and open responses. After the IDI process, I re-stated or summarized the information, then, presented it to them to vouch accuracy. The sharing of findings with the participants allows them to critically analyze and comment on it. The participants also affirmed that the summaries presented to them is an original reflection of their views, feelings, and experiences. In this study, their affirmation on the accuracy and completeness of the information contributed much to the credibility of the study. The data gathered from the IDI were organized accordingly into themes for analysis.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—

In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it's a flexible method which can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a

systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned was the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used man-

ual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as develop by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful tome in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—For Trustworthiness of the study, I adhered to credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability of qualitative study. Credibility. This is defined as the confidence that can be placed in the truth of the research findings. Credibility establishes whether the research findings represent plausible information drawn from the participants’ original data and is a correct interpretation of the participants’ original views. One of the key criteria addressed by researchers is that of internal validity, in which they seek to ensure that their study measures or tests what is actually intended. Guba and Lincoln (2009) argue that ensuring credibility is one of most important factors in establishing trustworthiness. In this study, credibility was considered during the interview process and even in the analysis

of data. I made sure that the responses of the participants were transcribed verbatim without adding to or rephrasing their answers. Transferability. The term ”transferability” refers to the extent to which the results of one study can be applied to a variety of circumstances (Silverman, 2001). The concern with positivist work is typically establishing that the results of the study at hand can be applied to a larger population. It is impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions of a qualitative study are relevant to other contexts and populations since qualitative findings are specialized to a small number of specific environments and individuals. Many naturalists feel that even conventional generalizability is impossible in practice since all observations are characterized by the individual situations in which they are

made. Dependability. In this study, I used approaches to address the issue of reliability to demonstrate that comparable results would be reached if the work was redone using the same procedures and circumstances. Guba and Lincoln (2008) emphasize the interconnectedness between credibility and dependability, stating that demonstrating the former goes a long way toward assuring the latter. This can be accomplished by combining tactics such as individual interviews to purposively selected different individuals. Confirmability. The qualitative investigator's concept of confirmability and objectivity

is a similar concern. In order to lessen the influence of bias, the importance of giving back and sharing the results to the participants in promoting such confirmability was highlighted once more to satisfy this part. The extent to which the researcher confesses his or her own predispositions, according to Miles and Huberman, is a significant factor for confirmability. In the study, part of the steps in analyzing the data were taken to ensure that the conclusions of the study are the result of the informants' experiences and thoughts, rather than my personal ideologies, qualities and preferences.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The participants revealed their experiences as they traversed and explored their lived experiences in becoming digital immigrants or technology experts in public elementary schools. The challenges of the kindergarten teachers in the post pandemic time, as well as their insights were determined particularly in Magpet, West District, Division of Cotabato. In this chapter, the results of the thematic analysis are presented. It is followed by discussions arranged according to themes and subthemes that were generated.

3.1. The lived experiences of kindergarten teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time—In analyzing the lived experiences of the public kindergarten school teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time, based on the interview answers shared by the teachers themselves (P1-P10), I was able to identify five (4) major themes. These are educators experiencing technological transitions, adaptability to change, becoming critical teachers, and hurdling technological constraints. Public kindergarten teachers have shared diverse and stimulating experiences as they adapt to the digital landscape of the 21st century. Despite the challenges, these

experiences are predominantly enriching and educational, motivating them to stay up-to-date with technology in their schools. A digital immigrant is commonly defined as an individual who was born and raised prior to the advent of the digital era. These individuals, usually belonging to Generation X/Xennial and preceding generations, did not have extensive exposure to computers or the internet during their formative years. As a result, they have had to adjust to the new vocabulary and methods associated with digital technology. The latter sections of the study focused on the detailed description and analysis of the teacher-researchers' personal experiences as participants. They identified themselves as digital immigrants in the context of the 21st century.

3.1.1. Experiencing Technological Transitions—

The notion of the digital immigrant emerged from the recognition that teachers encountered challenges in effectively interacting with the younger generation as a result of a disparity in technological proficiency; digital native learners employed a distinct language compared to their older, digital immigrant teachers. Typically, a digital immigrant refers to a someone who was born before the advent of technology, including the use of computers, the Internet, and cellphones. They usually experience technological and modernization transitions. Their utilization of internet technology, sometimes referred to as "immigration," is directly associated with the term immigrants. The participants were requested to provide their own definition and interpretation of digital immigrants. The majority of participants said that digital immigrants, in the context of teaching, refer to individuals who were born before the advent of computers and those who experienced technological transitions. This is the primary theme explored in this study. As defined by participant 1, a Digital Immigrant refers to an individual who was born prior to the widespread adoption of digital technology. They have had to acclimate to the digital realm, as opposed to being raised in it. They are individuals who have undergone a shift in their utilization of technology and are open to accepting it. P2 added that in his perspective, a Digital Immigrant might be described as a somebody who may not possess the same level of ease and familiarity with digital technology as their

3.1.2. Adaptability to Change—Teachers are recognized for their ability to adapt to change, acknowledging its continual nature. The study examines the extent to which teacher participants adjusted their thoughts, actions, and emotions as personal strategies to effectively address technology obstacles and advancements, demonstrating their adaptability to change. This entails altering their cognitive perspective to consider different options, implementing di-

verse strategies to effectively handle the situation, and reducing counterproductive or distracting emotions. The utilization of technology is not simply a compilation of tasks curated by a leader of an institution. However, it is essential for the teacher-participants to be dedicated to fostering the sustainability of learning and technological adaptability, as this has become a top academic concern in recent times. Participants who are unprepared for the conditions of rapid younger counterparts. While they may have a preference for conventional approaches, they are acquiring the skills to utilize technology. P3 summed up that a Digital Immigrant refers to an individual who has acquired knowledge and skills in using new technologies at a later stage of their life. While they may not readily embrace emerging digital trends, they provide a distinctive viewpoint in the realm of digital technology and are experiencing transitions. This is corroborated by the initial definition provided by Prensky (2001) on digital immigrants. He states that individuals who did not grow up during the digital period but later embraced the new technology are known as "digital immigrants," whereas those who were born during or after the digital era are known as "digital natives." The advent of the digital era commenced in 1980. Thus, based on Prensky's criteria, individuals who are 40 years old or above are categorized as digital immigrants. Modern individuals who are not native to the digital age actively participate in daily activities and pursue technology education to stay updated with current trends. However, the process of learning is characterized by a challenging combination of intricate emotions and the achievement of tasks. The educators who are not familiar with digital technology should be allocated an adequate amount of time to acquire the new skills, and they should be handled with sensitivity during the learning process.

verse strategies to effectively handle the situation, and reducing counterproductive or distracting emotions. The utilization of technology is not simply a compilation of tasks curated by a leader of an institution. However, it is essential for the teacher-participants to be dedicated to fostering the sustainability of learning and technological adaptability, as this has become a top academic concern in recent times. Participants who are unprepared for the conditions of rapid

technology change in their local settings may display an inability to focus on information flow and hamper their ability to stay updated with the latest technological trends in education. Participant 4 expressed that enhancing the interactivity and engagement of the pupils throughout lessons was gratifying where he witnessed learners' enjoyment of learning through this novel approach. To him, he was highly adaptable as an educator. P5 shared that the experience has been a challenging yet valuable opportunity for growth. She had observed the ways in which digital technologies may accommodate various learning styles, so enhancing the effectiveness of education. She found it highly satisfying to witness the learners flourish using these tools. Teachers' flexibility in embracing change facilitated the ease of everything. P6 added that the pursuit of digital literacy has presented him with both difficulties and rewards. Initially, he found it challenging to navigate through various applications and platforms. However, witnessing the passion of his learners while utilizing these tools justifies all the effort. The process of adapting required numerous nights without sleep, but the outcome justified the effort. Undoubtedly, the emergence and expansion of the

3.1.3. Becoming critical teachers—Critical teaching refers to instructional strategies that specifically aim to develop student thinking, while it has a broader scope. Teaching and learning processes are inherently interconnected. A strategically critical educator can be defined as a someone who possesses a deep understanding of instructional variables and is cognizant of the cognitive demands associated with learning. This consciousness results in a perception of appropriate timing and a managerial approach that utilizes technology as a tool. Strategic teachers are those who employ technology in their classroom instruction and are open to receiving training to enhance their digital proficiency in relation to classroom procedures and teach-

internet expedited the progress of technology throughout the preceding century. In the latter decade of the 20th century, firms that had access to the internet increased their impact, both domestically and internationally. The advent of the twenty-first century has brought about a significant transformation in communication through the emergence of social networks and mobile devices (Schallmo et al., 2017). The ongoing digital transformation is driven by enterprises committed to enhancing their information systems and digitizing their operations, which also encompasses technical developments in educational institutions (Osmundsen, 2020). Digital transformation refers to the creation of networks consisting of various actors, such as enterprises and customers, throughout the value chain, and the use of new technologies (Schallmo et al., 2017). Nevertheless, digital transformation extends beyond the mere use of technology; it must also consider alterations in individuals, culture, and organizational framework. Both the public and private sectors have adopted technological developments, although not consistently. However, this has contributed to their expansion (Jackson, 2019). This evolution has had a significant impact on schooling as well.

ing methods. Regardless of whether they are newcomers or experienced veterans, teachers consistently strive to enhance the efficacy and efficiency of their work by utilizing technology as a means of continuous learning. P8 discussed that he utilized technology to establish a connection between his classroom and the global community. They engage in virtual excursions, communicate with specialists via video conferences, and cooperate with classrooms worldwide on international initiatives. He adopted a discerning and evaluative approach as a teacher. P9 expressed that she employed technology to individualize instruction. Within the same digital platform, she had the capability to allocate distinct tasks to individual pupils according to

their specific requirements and capabilities. P10 shared that he employed technology to advance the concept of digital citizenship. He educated his students on the topics of online safety, digital etiquette, and the conscientious utilization of technology. They engaged in frequent discussions on these subjects and actively apply them in their online interconnections. This result is related to the research conducted by Jackson (2019) and Bond et al. (2018), both teachers and students now have the ability to use technologies and digital resources. As a result, schools are reconsidering their traditional teaching approaches and embracing continuous learning. Furthermore, in order to promote and guarantee the school's transition to digital platforms, it is imperative to cultivate the proficiency of both educators and learners in adapting to and utilizing sophisticated technology (Bond et al., 2018). Technological improvements have compelled users to acquire and adapt new skills, observe passively, and generate material. By engaging in these activities, educators and students can consistently acquire up-to-date knowledge and information regarding the digital realm as it pertains to education.

3.1.4. Hurdling technological constraints—Public school teachers faced several technological obstacles. Technology plays a crucial role in the educational process in the twenty-first century. When properly integrated into the classroom, computers, video conferencing, and even artificial intelligence can be used to enhance students' education, support children with disabilities, and offer several additional advantages and applications. Nevertheless, the integration of educational technology in the classroom is not consistently smooth or effective. The study found that the teachers encountered obstacles that prevented them from obtaining, implementing, and employing technology that could improve the educational experiences of their students. When inquired about the precise difficulties they faced, four

subthemes were identified. These are the lack of digital resources, intermittent connections, lack of cybersecurity and lack of expertise.

3.1.5. Lack of digital resources—The majority of participants highlighted that their primary obstacle in transitioning to digital immigrants or effectively utilizing technology in classrooms is the dearth of technological and digital tools. Consequently, it can be inferred that teachers were not equipped with digital software and technology within their classrooms. The teacher-participants had the belief that technology has the potential to enhance students' performance and academic accomplishments. Nevertheless, instructors have indicated that the primary obstacle to incorporating technology into the classroom is the insufficient allocation of resources towards gear, software, and wifi infrastructure. Access to contemporary technologies is significantly restricted. Participant 1 explained that An issue he had encountered was the absence of dependable internet connectivity for every student. This can lead to a disparity in access to digital resources, resulting in certain students being unable to fully engage in online educational activities. P3 shared that frequently, lectures can be interrupted by technical difficulties. Software malfunctions, device malfunctions, or server failures can result in substantial disruptions to the learning process. P4 added that some pupils lack the requisite devices for online learning. While certain students may possess a laptop or tablet in their household, others may solely possess a smartphone or lack any technological gadget. The integration of information technology in the classroom has become widespread, leading to the enhancement and replacement of obsolete teaching methods and tools. This allows teachers to proactively build curriculum that cater to individual student needs. Despite the fact that certain technologies may not have been initially intended for educational purposes, many teachers are still able to incorporate them into the classroom, even when faced

with limited technological resources (Zimlich, 2015). Curiously, Zimlich (2015) conducted a study where the professional performance of six graduates from the master's level certification program at the University of Alabama was observed to determine the efficiency of their lesson plans when utilizing technology. The study revealed that the amount and level of technological advancements in the classroom did not determine the success of technology implementation. Instead, the quality of the teacher's utilization of technology played a crucial role. This attribute enables the teachers to distinguish themselves in the pupils' memories.

3.1.6. Intermittent Connections—Undoubtedly, the Internet possesses immense potential to augment the caliber of education, particularly the quality of teaching experiences for educators, which is a fundamental aspect of sustained development in the field of education. Although it is important to acknowledge that the Internet is not a panacea for all educational challenges, it can facilitate the discovery of human abilities that can enrich the process of learning and teaching. Internet access is essential for individuals to become digital citizens, as it serves as the primary medium for the transmission of knowledge and information. It can enhance the quality of technology in several ways. It grants access to a plethora of knowledge, expertise, and educational resources, hence broadening learning opportunities beyond the confines of the classroom. Nevertheless, the participants in this study conveyed their frustration and the hindrance caused by sluggish internet disruptions when utilizing instructional technologies in the classroom. Participants 6, 7, and 9 expressed the same sentiments. It was evident that their sporadic internet connection impeded their ability to deliver adequate and high-quality classroom instructions. Despite the presence of laptops and other devices, the teachers said that the sluggish internet connections continue to impede their ability to work as technolog-

ically proficient educators in public schools. They moreover comprehend that having an internet connection is crucial for the functionality of their products. Devoid of signal or data, instructional technology serves no purpose. This finding is related to the study of Juergens (2020), that if a school does not have the necessary network infrastructure to support laptops and notebooks, providing a classroom full of students with a box of computers or notebooks will not be advantageous. An effective network architecture requires fast and reliable WIFI connectivity both at school and at home, together with robust data privacy and security measures, access to digital resources, and other essential components. It is crucial to carefully and strategically design, build, and manage a strong network infrastructure to ensure the ongoing efficient and responsible utilization of technology in education.

3.1.7. Lack of Cyber Security—Cybersecurity, at its most basic level, entails collective efforts to safeguard our data and ensure the integrity of our computer systems. Cybersecurity refers to the precise measures used to safeguard computer systems, networks, and confidential information from unauthorized access, which has the potential to threaten the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of such resources. Schools are attractive to hackers due to their abundance of personal information, which is often inadequately safeguarded compared to the cyber security measures employed by private companies. Malicious groups are eager to exploit the enormous expenditures managed by many institutions. The field of cybersecurity is dynamic, with constant advancements in systems and networks. The upcoming generation will be responsible for creating, maintaining, and enhancing these digital security measures. In the present era, our interconnection with technologies and individuals has reached unprecedented levels, and a significant portion of our data and resources are situated in the

realm of cyberspace. This finding is related to the efforts of the new Philippine administration, the foreign policy priorities and national security interests are confirmed. Although traditional security concerns will remain significant in decision-making, non-traditional security challenges have influenced the perception of security. Cybersecurity has become widely recognized as a critical concern for all entities, ranging from individuals to governments, due to the extensive consequences of cyber threats. During the period from 2016 to 2021, the Philippines made advancements in its efforts to join the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, establish the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT), and implement several national policies and programs. However, despite the positive progress, there are also noticeable challenges in the form of the country's inclination to react rather than proactively address issues, low prioritizing of cybersecurity, and an imbalanced focus. This policy brief has evaluated the country's cybersecurity position over the previous six years by analyzing the progress and problems in the field and identifying crucial themes. The policy proposals presented here aim to greatly contribute to the development of a resilient, advanced, and secure cyberspace in the Philippines, as the nation progresses in the face of constantly changing cyber threats.

3.1.8. Lack of expertise—In addition to acquiring technological gadgets, teachers must possess the knowledge and skills to proficiently operate and seamlessly incorporate these contemporary technology into their instructional practices. Currently, there has been a growing introduction of very innovative and sophisticated instructional technologies. During the study, teachers expressed a strong inclination not only to enhance their personal use of each new technology, but also to educate their students on how to use it effectively. Introducing a new technology in classrooms that is inac-

cessible to both teachers and students is unlikely to enhance any child's educational experience. Furthermore, expecting teachers to independently acquire the skills to apply this new tool can be exasperating and time-intensive. Providing professional training to teachers, faculty, and staff is a necessary investment of time and money in order to ensure that students achieve the desired outcomes from their use of technology. The teacher-participants encountered deficiencies in knowledge inside their respective schools. In order to keep up with the demands of technological advancement, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of their applications and functionalities. Participant 6 shared that Although digital technology offers numerous advantages, it also possesses certain disadvantages. It has come to his attention that certain students encountered difficulties in maintaining concentration while engaging in online learning, and establishing a sense of camaraderie within the classroom can be more challenging. As an educator, he also lacked the proficiency to execute his responsibilities employing intricate technologies. P8 also expressed that the advent of digital technology has facilitated seamless collaboration with fellow educators. The ability to exchange resources and ideas through online platforms has proven to be immensely beneficial. However, as a novice, he still had numerous concepts to grasp and he was still deficient in his proficiency in utilizing technology in the educational setting. This finding was supported by the conceptualization of Fucili (2020) that users of technology must gain the specific knowledge, information, and skills necessary to effectively use it for educational purposes. One of the difficulties is that users must invest time in learning new skills necessary to operate and implement the technology. The digital transformation of the classroom extends beyond the use of tools and software; it affects the users', teachers', and students' knowledge and abilities, as well

Fig. 3. The lived experiences of kindergarten teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time

as the didactics and procedures of educational institutions. Digital pedagogies, technological models, and adaptive, open, smart, and disruptive technologies all serve as examples of educational technology use (González-Pérez et al., 2019). With this, educational institution personnel must be vigilant and prepared to adapt to the changes brought about by digital transformation. Indeed, effective technology use is becoming an increasingly important skill, not just for the teachers in K-12 education, but also in students' lives after graduation. College courses are increasingly being provided online or in a

hybrid format that combines classroom instruction and online instruction. Even traditional classroom courses are increasingly utilizing e-learning tools (such as McGraw-Hill Connect and Pearson). Students who can navigate technology for e-learning and research purposes are better prepared for these college learning environments and careers, which will require prospective candidates to have a working knowledge of Microsoft Office products, strong typing skills, the ability to communicate via email, and the ability to manage digital calendars, among other skills

3.2. *The coping strategies of kindergarten teachers on the challenges they encountered in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time—*

The second research objective of this study focuses on the coping mechanisms of kindergarten teachers on the challenges they experienced in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time. Figure four (4) shows the summary of their coping strategies. As seen in Figure 4, the

coping strategies of teacher participants are divided into three (3) major themes. These are continuous professional development, personal learning, and collaborating with others. These summarized the coping strategies of the teachers as they deal with the challenges of the current research circumstances.

3.2.1. Continuous professional development—ICT integration in the classroom is crucial in the current digital age, as it provides students with the chance to acquire and apply the necessary skills for the 21st century. Conducting study on the issues and difficulties related to the use of ICT in education might help teachers overcome obstacles and become proficient technology users, as indicated by the participants in the interview. Given the intricate nature of ICT, implementing a clearly defined program of ICT-based training can aid educators in identifying and fulfilling the technological knowledge and skills that Filipino students require for their present academic, basic education, and future schooling needs. The participants of this study presented their ideas as to how they coped with some difficulties or challenges they experienced. Participant 7 mentioned that in order to stay abreast of the swift rate of technical advancements, she allocated a portion of her time every week to engage in professional development activities. She engaged in blog reading, webinars attendance, and active involvement in online learning forums. P1 shared that in order to address the difficulties associated with utilizing digital technology, She actively pursued possibilities for professional growth

and advancement. This entails participating in workshops and webinars, as well as being a member of online communities comprised of educators who exchange information and guidance. According to the concepts presented in Go Guardians (2019), a major challenge faced by teachers when incorporating technology in their classrooms is a deficiency in their knowledge and awareness of how to effectively utilize technology, or a feeling of unease when using it. Teachers who have these concerns also have challenges in accessing professional development tools that can equip them with the necessary knowledge and expertise to successfully and efficiently incorporate technology. Teachers should receive comprehensive training on how to effectively utilize the program to enhance digital learning in their classrooms. Teachers have the opportunity to engage with technological specialists for continuous support and guidance in utilizing Teacher. Additionally, they may avail themselves of a wide array of teacher resources that provide insights on incorporating technology in the classroom and maximizing the benefits of Teachers. This could perhaps serve as their mechanism for dealing with their challenges related to technology difficulties, acquiring knowledge, and navigating manipulations.

3.2.2. Personal Learning—Teachers are adept at embracing obstacles, as seen by their ability to adapt their personal approach when faced with difficult situations. During the study,

teacher-researchers who were participants indicated that in addition to attending ICT-based trainings and seminars, they also described how they personally adapt to become self-reliant in

dealing with the most difficult situations. The participants' self-sufficiency is apparent as they demonstrate their abilities and skills, and independently devise solutions to overcome the difficulties associated with transitioning into the digital world. Self-sufficiency is a crucial habit they used to overcome the challenges they encountered. Self-sufficiency refers to their ability to independently and proficiently master the technological discipline without relying on any other resources. They were in the process of acquiring knowledge and discovering methods independently. Participants 2, 6, and 8 explained the importance of personal learning to become technologically inclined. Participant 2 shared that he discovered that meticulous strategizing and thorough groundwork are crucial. Prior to implementing technology in the classroom, he made an effort to acquaint himself with its functionalities, and he consistently prepared contingency measures to address any potential technical issues. P6 added that regular introspection serves as an additional coping tool. He dedicated time to assess the effectiveness of various aspects and make appropriate modifications accordingly. These are his personal endeavors to enhance his proficiency in utilizing technology. P8 expressed that preserving an optimistic mindset and a capacity for amusement is beneficial. The field of technology might elicit feelings of

frustration, but it also presents an exhilarating prospect for fostering innovation and creativity in the realm of education. Continue to acquire knowledge. Go guardians (2019) supported this finding when they described the different challenges that schools may face when integrating technology in the classroom and how teachers can overcome them. While technology is increasingly being used in K-12 education, many teachers are still having difficulty incorporating it into their classes and are unsure whether doing so is the best move for them. There are several variables that each of us must consider (cost, convenience of use, and continuous assistance for correct understanding and use) when determining how, when, and if to introduce new technology. Teachers frequently face the following issues and concerns when integrating technology and digital media into the classroom: Students misusing technology, teacher knowledge and professional development, keeping students safe online, Cost of new technology and Keeping up with changes but teachers may start from developing their personal beliefs and motivation to become effective technology users. Teachers need to explore on their own when resources are not enough. This is where teachers' self-sufficiency became a strategy to overcome technological difficulties faced by the teachers in the study.

3.2.3. *Collaborating with others*—Support structures are essential for equipping teacher-participants with a strong basis in effectively implementing ICT-based instructions in the classroom. Particularly within this context, the participants conveyed their dependence on their colleagues and individuals with superior digital knowledge and skills. Providing informal or formal technical assistance to technology users who are facing difficulties was crucial in enhancing the participants' skill development in the study. Further they also considered the im-

portance of partnership with parents and other stakeholders. Participant 4 shared that he endeavored to engage parents and others. Parents have the ability to assist their children in their educational endeavors at home, particularly in regards to utilizing digital resources. P5 expressed that she discovered that engaging in collaboration with fellow educators is quite beneficial. Teachers may exchange ideas, resources, and tactics for proficiently utilizing digital technologies. P7 added that receiving assistance from colleagues and even students who

Fig. 4. The coping strategies of kindergarten teachers on the challenges they encountered in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time

are knowledgeable in technology has shown to be advantageous. They frequently provide a novel viewpoint or innovative ideas. The above discussions were supported by the notions of Kostaris et.al., (2017) that today, educators can become more focused on the needs of individual pupils through the use of technology in the classroom. Teaching is more student-centered than at any point in history thus asking for support and technical assistance from the others who are experts in this field may help those who are struggling

with the use of technology-based materials. Technology in the classroom has evolved from a single computer to several computers and Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) possibilities for students (Koivisto, 2014 and Syso, 2014). By the time kids reach high school, they should be able to navigate computer applications and utilize technology for educational purposes (Alsaeed, 2017). This all can be done by learning from others and enhancing our own practices as teachers.

3.3. Educational management insights drawn from the experiences and challenges of kinder teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time—The last research objective of this study focuses on the insights or lessons learned by the teacher-participants in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time. Figure five (5) shows the summary of insights and lessons

learned. Based on the experiences and challenges of the kinder teachers in public elementary schools, the participants of this study had their respective insights to further improve their experiences in becoming technologically inclined in schools. These insights were some of the personal thoughts of the participants that they deemed significant in understanding their real situations in the new normal. As seen in Figure 5, the insights of the participants are

divided into two major themes. These are the importance technological literacy in schools and the need to provide professional development trainings. These summarized the insights of the teachers based on their experiences in schools including the challenges and coping mechanisms. Based on their responses, although they

experienced struggles and success in the process, still their insights have always reminded them of the lessons and things that they learned which made them more equipped and competent as digitally transformed teachers in the new normal.

3.3.1. The importance technological literacy in schools—Although teachers encounter various challenges and concerns in schools on a daily basis, both positive and bad, they perceive the transition to becoming digital immigrants as an opportunity to adopt digital literacy in education. Despite some uncertainty, the majority of individuals still aspire to acquire technical abilities in the classroom, recognizing that embracing digital literacy leads to beneficial educational development. Transcripts revealed that participants consider digital literacy to be crucial for creating a presence in the modern world, particularly in the field of education. Teachers' lack of digital literacy hinders their capacity to do various tasks and obtain necessary resources. Teachers were able to enhance their teaching efficiency, gain access to resources, achieve fulfillment, and develop into educators equipped to instruct 21st century learners, all because to digital literacy. The instructors' responses portrayed a situation where they actively seek opportunities to enhance their technological proficiency, as it provides them with a multitude of alternatives. Notwithstanding the challenges they faced, they maintained a positive outlook on surmounting the requirements to attain digital literacy in the realm of education. The participants of this study had given their respective insights as to how they felt and what was their main learning about all their experiences in becoming technologically inclined in the classroom. P1 shared that an important realization she acquired is the significance of adaptability in educational administration. Thanks to

technology, learning is now unrestricted by the physical boundaries of the classroom or the limitations of school hours. As an educator, teachers should modify their instructional approaches to accommodate the demands of this novel learning setting. Proficiency in digital literacy is essential. P2 expressed that he discovered that technology can serve as an excellent instrument for differentiation. Every child acquires knowledge at their own unique speed, and digital resources have the capability to offer customized educational experiences that specifically address the requirements of each student. Therefore, teachers must consistently adopt and utilize technology. P3 added that to recognize the significance of digital literacy, not only for kids but also for teachers. Ongoing professional development in this field is essential for the efficient incorporation of technology into education. The finding pertains to the conception of Sjöberg and Lilja (2019), which suggests that universities worldwide have initiated the process of digital transformation by incorporating technology into their teaching, administrative, and communication procedures. At the university, instructional technology platforms and electronic communications, such as email and social media messages, are commonly utilized. In addition, the skills necessary for both education and employment have progressed in tandem with technology improvements. The emergence of the internet has coincided with the development of digital literacy, which requires individuals to possess the skills to retrieve, search, and evaluate information in a

discerning manner (Liu et al., 2020). The advent of social media platforms like YouTube and Pinterest, along with the widespread use of mobile devices, has empowered people to create digital content, showcasing their media literacy skills. With the progression of technology, certain skills will become outdated (UNESCO,

3.3.2. *The need to provide professional development trainings*—Enhancing practice relies on the fundamental elements of learning opportunities provided to teachers. Enhancing the technological literacy of our teachers will enable them to effectively utilize these skills in the classroom, thereby fostering the development of a robust understanding of digital citizenship among their students. Technologically literate teachers view technology as a source of infinite creative opportunities, rather than a set of instructions to be followed. Although digital literacy does not require mastery of digital tools, teachers should possess knowledge of these tools to fully leverage their teaching capabilities. Therefore, the study stressed the importance of attending diverse and pertinent training programs aimed at enhancing technology abilities. Utilizing digital media to enhance learning enables teachers to more effectively fulfill the needs of individual pupils. Despite having received training from the Department of Education, they expressed the need for extra training to enhance their technological proficiency and reach their maximum capabilities. P6 shared that he discovered that professional development is crucial for effectively incorporating technology into teaching. Teachers must consistently enhance their digital proficiency and acquire knowledge about the most recent tools and methodologies for using technology into their teaching. P7 expressed that technology has the ability to establish a connection between the classroom and the outside world. It can offer students a range of varied learning

2017). The ongoing challenge for organizations and individuals is in recognizing, adjusting to, and embracing advancements that are applicable to their own circumstances. Hence, it is imperative to adopt and actualize digital transformation.

experiences, introduce them to diverse cultures and ideas, and equip them for the interconnected globalized world. Therefore, it is imperative to provide teachers with training to develop proficiency in utilizing digital technology within educational institutions. Finally, P9 discussed that process of incorporating technology into various aspects of our lives is an ongoing and continuous process, rather than a fixed end goal. The focus is on consistently investigating, acquiring knowledge, and adjusting in order to utilize the advantages of technology for educational purposes. Therefore, it is necessary for DepEd to establish a systematic training program to enhance teachers' technological proficiency. A group of Experts called Go Guardians (2019) published an online article on the benefits of technology in the classroom. The benefits stretch far and wide for both teachers and students. Integrating computer technology into the classroom can serve as a means for teachers to support and enhance learning, create opportunities to connect with students, and encourage students to connect with information in new and exciting ways. With supportive guidance, clearly defined objectives, and attentive instruction on how to use technology effectively and responsibly, students are equipped with new skills as digital learners that have been linked to both improved academic performance and increased personal and career success. The benefits of integrating technology into the classroom include increased student engagement, Encouraging teamwork and collaboration, preparing students for life after graduation, Connecting

Fig. 5. Educational management insights drawn from the experiences and challenges of kinder teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time

students and teachers, Improved teaching outcomes, and Supporting differentiated instruction. With this, teachers may be trained purposefully to develop their technological skills to enhance teaching and learning experiences in schools.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the lived experiences, challenges encountered, coping mechanisms and insights of kinder teachers in utilizing digital technology in their kindergarten instructions in the post-pandemic time. The participants were coming from the schools of Magpet, West District, Division of Cotabato, Region XII. In order to accomplish the research goals, I employed a qualitative phenomenological approach, specifically utilizing thematic analysis. Following Creswell's (2006) recommendations, I conducted interviews using open-ended questions to gain an authentic comprehension of individuals' experiences. Moreover, through this interview method, I prompted participants to thoroughly and candidly discuss their personal interpretations and understandings of the phenomenon under investigation, namely the experiences of kindergarten teachers in transitioning to school digitalization.

4.1. Findings—

Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the teacher participants, the following themes were revealed. The lived experiences of teacher-participants in public elementary schools in becoming digital immigrants showed the following four major themes: educators experiencing technological transitions, adaptability to change, becoming critical teachers, and hurdling technological constraints. There were three sub-themes that emerged from the challenges encountered by

the participants. These are the lack of digital resources, intermittent connections, lack of cybersecurity and lack of expertise. The three coping mechanisms of teachers as participants in the challenges they experienced were: continuous professional development, personal learning, and collaborating with others. The two educational management insights drawn from the participants were the importance technological literacy in schools and the need to provide professional development trainings.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Teachers perceive the new generation of learners as digital natives, contrasting themselves as digital immigrants who acquired computer and technological skills later in life, rather than being born into the digital age. Teachers demonstrate adaptability by modifying their practices as personal mechanisms to effectively respond to technological challenges and improvements. Teacher-participants demonstrate a strategic approach in effectively using technology in their profession and consistently seek to enhance their digital proficiency in relation to classroom procedures and teaching methods. They faced technological obstacles that prevented them from obtaining, installing, and using technologies that may improve the educational experiences of their students. Teachers have hurdles in acquiring digital and technical literacy. The primary obstacle preventing them from becoming digital immigrants or effectively using technology in classrooms is the insufficient availability of technological tools in schools. Acquiring and sustaining technology in schools proved to be a costly undertaking for them, as they typically relied on personal funds to procure their technological requirements. In addition, they conveyed their dissatisfaction with sluggish internet speeds and disruptions, which impede their ability to utilize educational technologies

in the classroom. In order to keep up with the demands of technological advancements, teachers must also possess a comprehensive understanding of their applications and functionalities, which may sometimes result in knowledge gaps. Ensuring the safety of learners is one of the difficulties that necessitates the practice of data privacy. Teachers encountered diverse obstacles in adapting to the digital age, but their strategies for dealing with these challenges enabled them to effectively fulfill their roles as educators in the 21st century. Teachers filled their knowledge gaps by engaging in various ICT-based trainings with the goal of becoming proficient technology users. Additionally, they adapt personally to achieve self-reliance in their approach to dealing with the most demanding technology scenarios. Teachers must have a strong understanding of how to effectively use ICT-based instruction in the classroom, and this requires support structures. They depended on their colleagues and those with superior expertise in digital knowledge and skills. The specialists' technological aid proved exceedingly beneficial for them. In addition, teachers, who are considered digital immigrants, acknowledge their uncertainty in employing technology in the classroom. However, they are still motivated to acquire technical abilities, as they believe that adopting digital literacy will lead to good transformation in education. The acquisi-

tion of digital literacy skills enabled them to enhance their teaching effectiveness, gain access to a wider range of resources, achieve personal satisfaction, and transform into educators who are adept at preparing students for the demands of the 21st century. Despite having received trainings from the Department of Education, they expressed the need for additional trainings to enhance their technological competence and reach their maximum potential. The findings of this study shed light on the various experi-

ences of public elementary school teachers in becoming digital immigrants in schools. The study looked into the educators' actions and reactions. These experiences, acquired through systematic interviews, may help other educators interested in the phenomenon under study, as well as other scholars pursuing comparable lines of study. Participants' coping techniques can be used as a resource for those who find themselves in a similar position.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The Department of Education may create rules, programs, and activities, such as continuing education and in-service training, with the aim of enhancing teachers' proficiency and expertise in technology and digital literacy inside schools. This professional development initiative may prioritize the incorporation of technology in teaching. School leaders and administrators may establish school-based training sessions through Learning Action Cells (LAC). These sessions may assist teachers in developing the necessary skills to overcome knowledge gaps

that hinder their ability to adapt to digital technology. Additionally, they may guarantee the availability of sufficient technical, administrative, and collegial support for teachers. The policymakers, such as the government, may offer supplementary resources, such as educational technology and appropriate gadgets, to support the teaching and learning activities in schools. The WIFI providers should be encouraged to enhance their services and networks in order to enhance the technological experiences of teachers and students in schools. Future researchers may embark on the same research with different participants, places, and schools. Other avenues not scrutinized in this research may also be explored.

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